

KEY DRIVERS OF GRADE 6 PUPILS' READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Reading comprehension skills play a significant role for students to be successful in their academic life. However, there is still a significant knowledge gap concerning how the key drivers specifically influence the reading comprehension of sixth-grade students. This descriptive-correlational study was conducted to determine the influence of motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies on Grade 6 pupils' reading comprehension skills in a district of Misamis Oriental. The participants in this study were 159 Grade 6 pupils who were determined using the Taro Yamane formula. The researcher modified the research instruments from various authors and studies. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression. Findings revealed that the motivation to read and attention span were rated generally high by the participants. Meanwhile, home literacy environment and the teacher's reading strategies were rated as generally very good. The four sub-skills of reading comprehension – noting details, identifying the main idea, making inferences, and drawing conclusions got fair results. Results of regression analysis showed that the whole model is significant, implying that enhancing pupils' home literacy environment and teachers' reading strategies can improve learners' reading comprehension. Thus, parents are encouraged to have reading-friendly surroundings at home to foster a positive attitude toward reading, teachers may implement helpful reading strategies to reinforce pupils' reading abilities, and future researchers may examine other potential factors affecting reading comprehension skills.

Keywords: *motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, teachers' reading strategies, reading comprehension skills*

INTRODUCTION

Reading has always been a part of every individual's life. It is one of the basic foundations of learning and helps a person understand everything. Within the classroom setting, reading proficiency represents a fundamental language skill that is central to the learning process. A child's ability to read effectively has a major impact on their understanding and retention of new concepts. Haswani et al. (2024) define reading as the capacity to interpret written text to create meaning, highlighting its importance for academic performance. For some students, reading is a leisure and a hobby that keeps them aware of many things, but for some, it is a struggle that they continue to hurdle in their schooling and into their adult life. Even though a student may be proficient in reading certain words, reading comprehension is a skill that all students should acquire, work on, and master over time.

The problem of reading comprehension among students is not something new for many educators. It is a worldwide phenomenon, especially for learners who have difficulty understanding what they read. In fact, in the school where the researcher is teaching, he has observed that some Grade Six students do not know what they are reading and seem to be unmotivated in their studies. This is manifested in their attendance and submission of assignments/performance tasks and scores in tests. Moreover, only a few parents come to school during parent-teacher consultations to avail themselves of such consultations.

In the Philippines, where literacy rates significantly impact socio-economic development, the significance of reading proficiency cannot be emphasized enough. While the government in the Philippines has initiated various programs aimed at improving literacy, research conducted recently (Idulog et al., 2023) revealed that many Filipino students still encounter challenges in understanding what they read. In the elementary level, particularly grade 6, this grade level represents a vital phase in a student's educational path as they move from elementary to secondary education. Out of 79 participating nations, the Philippines had the lowest reading comprehension score in 2018. By 2022, it improved slightly to 76th out of 81 countries (PISA, 2022). In the Division of El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, the results of the reading assessments show that there is a need for intervention in reading comprehension. For these reasons, the researcher would like to find out how these key drivers in post-pandemic could influence the development of reading comprehension of elementary pupils, particularly in Grade 6.

The researcher believes that these key drivers would affect their development, particularly in their reading comprehension skills. Even though these aspects have been acknowledged, there is still a significant knowledge gap concerning how these key influences—motivation, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies—specifically affect the reading comprehension of sixth-grade students, particularly in El Salvador City. While global and national studies show broad patterns in reading comprehension issues, they frequently fail to address localized solutions geared toward this group.

The reading skills of elementary pupils today have been affected by various factors, including the effect of the post-pandemic mode of learning. Hence, the researcher would like to analyze how motivation, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies could impact the reading comprehension skills of these grade 6 elementary pupils in El Salvador City, province of Misamis Oriental.

A fundamental aspect of quality education is the development of strong literacy skills, with reading comprehension being a cornerstone of this study; therefore, the results of this study are consistent with UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goal 4, which advocates for quality and fair education for all, as well as the encouragement of lifelong learning. Since this study delves into factors that significantly impact the quality of education, specifically the reading comprehension, understanding the role of motivation, attention, home environment, and teaching strategies can inform interventions and policies aimed at improving the quality of education.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The researcher assumed that students' motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies have a bearing on their reading comprehension. It is logical to believe that motivated students, attentive, well-guided, and exposed to various reading strategies, have better reading skills. This study has its theoretical underpinnings from John Piaget's Cognitive Developmental Theory & Constructivist Theory, Schema Theory, the intrinsic-extrinsic theory of reading motivation, and Self-Regulation Theory.

Children build their own learning through interactions and experiences in their surroundings, according to the cognitive developmental theory of Jean Piaget (1972). Piaget believed that children actively participate in their own learning by engaging in behaviors such as exploration, experimentation, and observation. Through these actions, they actively construct their understanding of the world, much like young scientists (Cherry, 2024). Youngsters actively create information based on their prior knowledge and developmental stage. Children develop internal mental frameworks to understand their experiences as they interact with their surroundings. Constructivism may also depict the development of children as a sequence of successive phases. The nature of the reading environment within a child's home, including factors like access to books and encouragement of reading, has a considerable effect on their ability to understand what they read. As they learn, it is not only the school environment that matters, but also the kind of home environment in which a child receives support in terms of literacy. Therefore, a child's environment clearly has a strong effect on the growth of their thinking skills, notably their reading comprehension.

According to schema theory (1984), a reader's existing knowledge interacts with the text to improve their comprehension. Reading involves our brain's use of prior knowledge, or schemata, to extract and interpret textual information, which in turn supports our understanding and recall (Liu Le, 2020). In order for a child to have a better comprehension of the text they read, it requires their ability to relate it to previous

knowledge. The idea that children use their past knowledge to understand and learn from the texts read is explained in this theory. Schema theory is grounded in the idea that written language is not essentially meaningful, but instead, it teaches readers, such as children on how to pull meaning from their existing knowledge.

In addition, developing the reading comprehension skills of children is important because it allows them to understand the elements of a text, which include facts, ideas, vocabulary, events, and clear information. This basic skill increases overall understanding and prepares them for deeper analysis. It entails acquiring information or detailed answers to inquiries that begin with "what, where, when, who," etc. Clear and direct answers to questions from a text are essential for literal understanding. According to Nurjanah and Putri (2022), kids must learn to read literally because it is the lowest level of comprehension and is, therefore, considered significant. From their research, kids who demonstrated strong and very good literal reading comprehension also demonstrated good interpretative, critical, and creative reading comprehension skills.

The variable of motivation is foremost an essential influence for the increase of a pupil's reading skills. As Hairul et al. (2020) found, when students feel motivated to read, it creates a positive cycle. This motivation leads them to read more, which in turn can substantially improve their ability to understand what they are reading. According to Hairul et al. (2020), when students are really driven to read, they usually recognize its importance and are more likely to succeed at it. This reading motivation involves a person's aims, their convictions about reading, and their emotions connected to it—the 'why,' 'how,' and 'what for' of their reading experiences. Because motivation is so crucial in making reading enjoyable and understandable, it warrants greater emphasis.

Self-Regulation Theory (1996) describes how people control their behavior to avoid unfavorable outcomes and achieve their goals. It looks at how we regulate our feelings, ideas, and actions to stay focused and avoid distractions or harmful tendencies. This implies that students should make a conscious effort to maintain focus and attention during learning activities. Strong self-regulation abilities, for instance, enable sixth graders to focus on their work, block out distractions, and keep improving reading comprehension.

As mentioned in the cognitive development theory of Jean Piaget, the third and fourth variables, namely, home literacy environment and teachers' reading strategies, influence the reading comprehension skills of children since they actively construct their knowledge through interaction with their environment. As active learners, these children create meaning through exploration, hands-on activities, and interactions with people in their surroundings. Children who grow up in literacy-supportive homes can develop their schemas for language, narrative structure, and print concepts through rich, meaningful experiences. Teachers who support reading development by creating developmentally appropriate learning experiences would help children assimilate new knowledge and develop a love for reading.

Research Questions

The researcher aimed to determine the influence of motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies on the reading comprehension skills of Grade 6 pupils of District 1 in El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, for the SY 2024-2025.

Specifically, this research addressed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' level of motivation to read?
2. What is the participants' level of attention span?
3. What is the participant's self-report of their home literacy environment?
4. What is the participant's assessment of their teachers' reading strategies?
5. What is the participants' level of reading comprehension skills in terms of:
 - 5.1 Noting Details;
 - 5.2 Identifying the Main Idea;
 - 5.3 Making Inferences; and
 - 5.4 Drawing Conclusions?
6. Do the participants' motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and assessment of their teachers' reading strategies significantly influence their reading comprehension skills?

Hypotheses

Problems 1 to 5 are hypotheses-free, except for Problem 6, which has the null hypothesis indicated below.

Ho1: The participants' motivation to read does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho2: The participants' attention span does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho3: The participants' home literacy environment does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho4: The participants' assessment of their teachers' reading strategies does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation showing the Interplay of Variables in the Study

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design to characterize and ascertain the influence of factors such as motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies on the reading comprehension skills of sixth-grade pupils. Quantitative research with the help of a survey questionnaire was used in conducting this study. This descriptive-correlational design intended to both describe variables (motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, teachers' reading strategies, and reading comprehension skills) and examine the relationship between them. This design was appropriate because it enables the researcher to measure the degree of association between these factors without manipulating any variables.

According to Bhandari (2020), quantitative research is a helpful tool for identifying trends, calculating averages, making predictions, or examining cause-and-effect relationships. This research approach is particularly valuable for analyzing the connections between various factors—such as reading motivation, attention span, the home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies—and students' reading comprehension skills through the use of statistical analysis.

Participants of the Study and Sampling Procedure

This study involved 159 Grade 6 pupils as the participants with the following criteria: The pupil is a legitimate elementary learner and currently enrolled within the four public schools of District I in the Division of El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, and has given an assent form from their parents.

In order to ensure that the participants of this study are registered with their guardian's informed consent respecting ethical standards and protecting the child's autonomy, parental consent is necessary. The assent form ensures that the parents are fully aware of this study's purpose, methodology, and any potential risks involved. It also guarantees that this study has parental support, allowing for further monitoring of participant well-being during the research process.

This study used the Taro Yamane Formula to select participants from the total enrolled Grade 6 pupils in four (4) public elementary schools in District I of El Salvador City. A sample size with a total of 159 participants was proportionally chosen using stratified random sampling. This study used stratified random sampling to randomly select an equal number of participants based on the total number of enrolled grade 6 pupils in each participating school of District 1. Stratified random sampling is a technique where researchers divide a population into smaller, more specific groups, or "strata," based on shared traits or characteristics. Once these groups are formed, participants are randomly selected from each one to ensure the resulting sample is more balanced and accurately reflects the overall population (Simkus, 2024). The researcher gathered the list of public elementary schools in District I of El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, and to collate the total number of grade 6 pupils, a random stratified sampling was used to identify the number of participants in each school.

For this study, stratified random sampling was the suitable sampling technique since it guarantees that the sample was representative of the various demographic subgroups, in this case, the different public elementary schools in District I of El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental. The researcher can proportionately choose participants from each school based on its overall enrollment using stratified random selection, which is useful because there are several schools with different numbers of sixth-graders. The generalizability of the study findings throughout the district depends on this method's guarantee that every school is fairly represented. By using this method, the researcher addressed potential biases that could arise if the sample were to be selected purely at random from the entire district.

Research Instruments

The research instruments in this study were structured questionnaires that included items related to reading motivation, attention span, home literacy environment, teachers' reading strategies, and reading comprehension skills. The questionnaires were adopted and modified to gather quantitative data and analyzed statistically. The instruments that were utilized in this study consisted of the following:

For motivation to read, the researcher adapted a 5-point scale type of reading motivation questionnaire of Esponda-Pérez et al. (2023). The questionnaire included 10 items for intrinsic motivation and 10 items for extrinsic motivation.

For attention span, the researcher used and modified the questionnaire adopted by Barry Gilbert Laing, Suganthi Ramasamy and Marilyn Dina Anak Moses in their study

entitled *The Effect of Attention Span on Student Learning Engagement with a 5-point Likert scale*. The questionnaire contained 10 items.

For the home literacy environment variable, the researcher adapted and modified a 5-point scale survey questionnaire of Mildred Lerios Dumlao from her study entitled *Home Literacy Environments and the Reading Levels of Grade 2 Learners: Foundation for Enhanced Home Reading Program* which was published in 2024. This variable of home literacy environment had 10 items.

For teachers' reading strategies variable, the researcher adapted and modified a 5-point scale survey questionnaire. Some items were teaching styles: conceptualization and investigation, *Journal of Learning Styles*, 2(3), 3–19.

For the reading comprehension skills, the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Assessment Tool, a standardized reading comprehension evaluation, was used by the researcher. The test questions used for this study targeted the pupils' reading comprehension skills in terms of noting details, making inferences, identifying the main idea, and drawing conclusions.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher sought ethical clearance from the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of Lourdes College. When permission was granted, the researcher asked permission from the Division Superintendent for approval. When the approval was sought, the researcher communicated with the School Principal or School Head of the participating elementary schools. Then, the researcher communicated with the grade 6 advisers on the conduct of the study for the pupils. The researcher then prepared a letter of assent for the pupils. Then, the forms were given to the students' parents through the class advisers. After the collection of letters of assent, the researcher personally floated out the questionnaires.

The materials that were prepared by the researcher in the collection of data are the following: a Letter of Permission to the School Principal to conduct the study, a Letter of Assent to the Pupil Participants, and the printed hard copies of the questionnaires for the grade 6 pupil participants. After the researcher gave the instructions, the class adviser helped in facilitating the questionnaires to the grade 6 pupils. The conduct of this study ensured that the classes of the participants were not disrupted; hence, the researcher followed accordingly with the class advisers/teachers in terms of the agreed time to conduct the survey. Thereafter, the accomplished questionnaires were organized, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The following statements are the statistical treatments that were employed for the research questions of this study:

For Problems 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, descriptive statistics such as the frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were employed to describe the participants' reading motivation, attention span, home literacy environment, assessment of their teachers' reading strategies, and reading comprehension skills.

Meanwhile, the analysis for Problem 6 used regression analysis to determine the influence of reading motivation, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies on the reading comprehension skills of Grade 6 pupils. The research checked the assumptions through scatterplots, residual plots, histograms, Q-Q plots, Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic, and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question 1. What is the participants' level of motivation to read?

The data showed an overall ($M = 3.81$, $SD = 0.59$), which had a high interpretation. Specifically, 54.09 percent of participants fell into the "High" category, indicating that half of the participants are highly motivated. Also, 31.45 percent demonstrate "Moderate" motivation, 13.21 percent show "Very High" motivation, and 1.26 percent report "Low" motivation. Importantly, no students reported "Very Low" motivation.

High motivation in reading implies that pupils are driven to read because of internal and external rewards. Internal rewards, such as enjoyment, curiosity, personal growth, and external rewards, like recognition and incentives, motivate children to engage in reading. These pupils find reading inherently satisfying and likely to participate in reading activities, leading to a deeper comprehension and a lifelong appreciation for narratives.

Table 1 - Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Motivation to Read

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	21	13.21
3.51-4.50	High	86	54.09
2.51-3.50	Moderate	50	31.45
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.26
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		159	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation			3.81 High
SD			0.59

Research Question 2. What is the participants' level of attention span?

The data reveal that they rated their attention span as high, with an overall ($M = 3.70$) and ($SD = 0.51$). Moreover, a high attention span suggests that students can keep focus during learning activities, follow through on tasks, and engage effectively in class discussions. This ability is crucial for academic success as it enables students to process and keep information, complete assignments, and actively participate in classroom activities without frequent distractions.

In this manner, more than half of the participants, or 57.86 percent, fell within the "High" category, while 3.77 percent exhibited a "Very High" attention span. A considerable 37.11 percent of the students showed a "Moderate" attention span, and only 1.26 percent fell within the "Low" category. Notably, no participant reported "Very Low" attention span.

Table 2 - Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Attention Span

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	6	3.77
3.51-4.50	High	92	57.86
2.51-3.50	Moderate	59	37.11
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.26
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		159	100.0
Overall Mean			3.70
Interpretation			High
SD			0.51

Research Question 3. What is the participant's self-report of their home literacy environment?

With an overall ($M = 3.51$) and ($SD = 0.61$), the data reveal that pupils rated their home literacy environment as very good. This indicates that, in general, pupils perceive their home environments as conducive to their literacy development. Most of the participants, or 46.54 percent, assessed their home literacy environment as "Very Good", while 43.40 percent assessed it as "Good". Fewer participants rated their home literacy environment "Fair" with 6.92 percent, and only 3.14 percent rated it as "Outstanding". Remarkably, none of the participants assessed their home literacy environment as "Poor".

Moreover, an effective home literacy environment is where parents help their kids read and other literacy-related activities, give them reading resources, and encourage participatory discussions. It has been demonstrated that a home environment full of literacy activities encourages early reading development, improves vocabulary acquisition, and cultivates a love of reading. The findings indicate that children who have

their parents support them in reading and discussing books are more likely to become more motivated to read on their own and to acquire stronger literacy skills.

Table 3 - Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Self-Report of their Home Literacy Environment

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Outstanding	5	3.14
3.51-4.50	Very Good	74	46.54
2.51-3.50	Good	69	43.40
1.51-2.50	Fair	11	6.92
1.00-1.50	Poor	0	0.00
Total		159	100.0
Overall Mean		3.51	
Interpretation		Very Good	
SD		0.61	

Research Question 4. What is the participant's assessment of their teachers' reading strategies?

The data reveal that they assessed their teachers' reading strategies as "Very Good", with an overall (M = 3.82, SD = 0.81). From the findings, according to participants' perceptions, their teachers utilize reading techniques that enhance literacy growth and understanding. Most participants, 37.11 percent, rated their teachers' reading strategies as "Very Good", while 23.27 percent found them to be "Outstanding". Additionally, 32.70 percent considered their teachers' reading strategies as "Good", and 6.92 percent believed them "Fair". Remarkably, no participants rated their teachers' reading strategies as "Poor".

Table 4 - Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of their Teachers' Reading Strategies

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Outstanding	37	23.27
3.51-4.50	Very Good	59	37.11
2.51-3.50	Good	52	32.70
1.51-2.50	Fair	11	6.92
1.00-1.50	Poor	0	0.00
Total		159	100.0
Overall Mean		3.82	
Interpretation		Very Good	
SD		0.81	

Research Question 5. What is the participants' level of reading comprehension skills in terms of:

- 5.1 Noting Details;**
- 5.2 Identifying the Main Idea;**
- 5.3 Making Inferences; and,**
- 5.4 Drawing Conclusions?**

Table 5 presents the summary table of participants' level of reading comprehension skills. The data reveal a consistent interpretation across each sub-area, with an overall mean of 3.21 and an overall standard deviation of 0.59. Subsequently, among the four assessed sub-skills, Noting Details received the highest (M = 3.88), followed by Identifying the Main Idea (M = 3.56) and Drawing Conclusions (M = 3.01). However, Making Inferences had the lowest (M = 2.40), suggesting that this is the most challenging aspect of reading comprehension for the participants.

The data analysis of participants' reading comprehension skills across four dimensions—Noting Details, Identifying the Main Idea, Making Inferences, and Drawing Conclusions—revealed an overall (M = 3.21), interpreted as "Fair". This shows that while kids exhibit core understanding abilities, there is a remarkable space for growth, particularly in higher-order thinking capabilities.

Table 5 - Summary Table of Level of Reading Comprehension Skills

Dimensions of Reading Comprehension Skills	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Noting Details	3.88	Fair	1.55
Identifying the Main Idea	3.56	Fair	1.83
Making Inferences	2.40	Fair	1.22
Drawing Conclusions	3.01	Fair	1.40
Overall	3.21	Fair	0.99

Research Question 6. Do the participants' motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and teachers' reading strategies significantly influence their reading comprehension skills?

Ho1: The participants' motivation to read does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho2: The participants' attention span does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho3: The participants' home literacy environment does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Ho4: The participants' assessment of their teachers' reading strategies does not significantly influence their reading comprehension skills.

Table 6 presents the regression analysis of the influence of participants' motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and assessment of teachers' reading strategies on their reading comprehension skills. This statistical tool was used after meeting the assumptions of regression (The Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic is .200; VIF ranges from 1.383 to 2.290; the histogram and QQ plot are found in the appendix). Data show that the whole model is significant with $F(4,154) = 5.83, p = .001$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that the combined influence of motivation to read, attention span, home literacy environment, and assessment of teachers' reading strategies significantly affects the participants' reading comprehension skills.

Table 6 - Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Motivation to Read, Attention Span, Home Literacy Environment, and Assessment of Teachers' Reading Strategies on their Reading Comprehension Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.12	.625	1.79	.075
Motivation	-.258	.182	-1.42	.159
Attention Span	.225	.169	1.33	.187
Home Literacy Environment	.364	.183	1.99*	.048
Assessment of Teachers' Reading Strategies	.251	.126	1.99*	.048

Model Summary

R= .371 R²= .137 Adjusted R²= .109 F (5,153) = 4.87**, p=.001

**significant at 0.01 level

*significant at 0.05 level

Furthermore, 13.7 percent of the variability of the participants' reading comprehension skills is accounted for by a combination of the predictor variables. The remaining 86.3 percent may be attributed to other factors not covered in this study, for instance, vocabulary knowledge, prior knowledge, cognitive abilities, reading fluency, socio-economic status, and access to diverse reading materials.

Taken individually, the regression analysis revealed that the home literacy environment ($t = 1.99, p = .048$) significantly influenced the reading comprehension of the participants, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. From the findings of this study, there is evidence that the home literacy environment significantly influences the reading

comprehension skills of Grade 6 pupils. This means that if the home literacy environment is well-established, it will contribute to the development of their comprehension skills.

Moreover, the regression analysis revealed that the assessment of teachers' reading strategies ($t = 1.99$, $p = .048$) significantly influences the reading comprehension of the participants, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. From the findings of this study, there is evidence that teachers' reading strategies significantly influence the reading comprehension skills of grade 6 pupils. This means that students who perceive their teachers' reading strategies as effective tend to perform better in reading comprehension.

On the other hand, the regression analysis revealed that the variables on motivation to read ($\beta = -.154$, $t = -1.42$, $p = .159$) and attention span ($\beta = .117$, $t = 1.33$, $p = .187$) do not significantly predict reading comprehension skills in this model. Although these variables may contribute to students' reading abilities, their effects are not strong enough to be statistically significant in this study.

Conclusions

The overall model is significant, which means that the combined influence of these key drivers plays a crucial role in the reading comprehension skills of grade 6 pupils. Moreover, enhancing the pupils' home literacy environment and teachers' reading strategies can lead to better outcomes. Among the four independent variables in this study, the home literacy environment and teachers' reading strategies were emphasized in their significance in the reading comprehension skills of grade 6 pupils.

Therefore, the theories confirmed in this study are John Piaget's Cognitive Developmental Theory & Constructivist Theory, Schema Theory, the intrinsic-extrinsic theory of reading motivation, and Self-Regulation Theory. It is evident that environmental factors have a significant impact on a child's cognitive development, including comprehension abilities, as it can be aligned with the findings on variables of home literacy environment and teachers' reading strategies in this study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions derived from this study, the following recommendations were taken for consideration:

1. **For parents**, they are encouraged to help cultivate a reading-friendly environment at home by providing their children with age-appropriate books, taking part in reading activities with them, and nurturing a positive attitude toward reading.
2. **For teachers**, they may continue to utilize helpful teaching strategies and implement evidence-based reading strategies, like guided reading, questioning techniques, and interactive discussions, in reinforcing pupils' reading comprehension skills.

3. **For school administrators**, they may include during SLAC sessions the integration of classroom activities that promote analysis, synthesis, and evaluation in reading lessons. They may encourage collaborative learning through group reading activities, peer discussions, and storytelling sessions among pupils.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For ethical considerations, the researcher anchored this study to the Belmont Report, which follows the three fundamental principles for ethical research: Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice. The researcher made it clear to the participants that their participation was purely voluntary and that their responses were kept with the utmost confidentiality and anonymity based on the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher in this study has no personal or professional relationship with the participants, ensuring objectivity and eliminating any potential conflict of interest in conducting this study.

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